

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Carnegie Endowment (2017): Global Protest Tracker (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/2CB6C216-7D34-4B94-9992-2748C5C6A110>

Abstract

The Global Protest Tracker is a project realized by Carnegie (Endowment for International Peace). The dataset covers over 700 significant anti-government protests worldwide (in 147 countries) in the time period from 2017 to the latest update in June 2024. As of summer 2024, work on the data collection seems to be continuing. Of the 700+ total entries in this dataset, there are 57 events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data (1). The data review includes a link to the official Global Protest Tracker website from which both the dataset, as well as all information listed here, is available.

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Data Review – Global Protest Tracker

The Global Protest Tracker is a project realized by Carnegie (Endowment for International Peace). The dataset covers over 700 significant antigovernment protests worldwide (in 147 countries) in the timespan from 2017 to the latest update in June 2024. As of summer 2024, work on the data collection seems to be continuing. Of the 700+ total entries in this dataset, there are 57 events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data (1).

This dataset focuses on significant anti-government protests. The research team defines the significance of a protest as follows: *“The word significant here is understood in terms of political importance: the impact of a protest on a country’s political life. While a protest’s size can give some indication of its importance, it is not determinative on its own.”* (1). A further influence on the decision whether or not a protest counts as significant is the “Freedom in the World” ranking of the given country (which reflects the status of political rights and civil liberties within a given country), since in some countries there are significantly more risks involved when protesting than in others. Based on this, if a country is considered “free” or “partly free” in the ranking, a protest is considered as significant if the peak size of the protest reaches at least 10.000 protesters, while in countries considered as “not free” a peak size of 1.000 protesters is enough for it to count as significant (1).

An exception to the significance considerations are protests directly related to the coronavirus outbreak, which were included because of their estimated influence on governance and policies at the local, national and even international level (1).

The data is based on reports from credible news sources, with cross-referencing to verify information when possible. Publications and television outlets used while compiling the data include but are not limited to: The Guardian, New York Times, Washington Post and many others. For a more extensive list please refer to the official Global Protest Tracker website (1).

The data is compiled as an interactive, tabular dashboard listing the country, protest name, start date of the protest, peak size of participants, underlying motivation behind the protest (economic, political, corruption), duration of the protest as well as the status of the concerned country in the “Freedom of the World” ranking. For more detailed information on a protest of interest the “+” button in front of the country’s name offers information on the trigger of the protest, more detailed information on the motivation of the protesters, the key participants as well as the outcome. The variable “outcome” focuses on the direct result of either a policy- or leadership change. If a change of policy or leadership occurs later down the line, even if the protests listed in this dataset might have been one of many causal factors that led to this change, that result is not considered in this dataset, since no change followed in the short term of, or during the protest (1).

While browsing the data, the user has the option to make use of multiple filter options: (A) ACTIVE, lists only ongoing protests, (B) LARGE, lists only protests with 100.000+ participants, (C) VIOLENT, lists only protests that experienced violent government crackdowns, (D) LONG, lists only protests which cover a duration of 3+ months, (E) OUTCOME, only lists protests that resulted in a significant government policy or leadership change and (E) COVID 19, which only lists protests concerning the pandemic. On top of these filter options there is also the option to search for specific keywords or sort the entries by e.g. peak size, enabling the user to quickly find what they may be looking for (1).

Limitations of the dataset include both a reliance on English-language news sources only, as well as possible inaccuracies in the protest size numbers provided since the only source of information were often either local authorities, who tend to underestimate the actual number of protesters, or the protest organizers who in turn tend to overestimate the number of participants (1).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Number of Entries
Armenia	5
Azerbaijan	4
Belarus	4
Georgia	10
Kazakhstan	5
Kyrgyzstan	8
Moldova	2
Russia	13
Tajikistan	1
Turkmenistan	1
Ukraine	3
Uzbekistan	1
Total Entries	57

Sources:

(1) Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Global Protest Tracker: ABOUT THE TRACKER. <https://carnegieendowment.org/features/global-protest-tracker?lang=en>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.